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Chitosan-based Coatings for Corrosion Protection of Biodegradable Mg Alloys

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Biodegradable metallic materials have outstanding potential in biomedical applications as they can be dissolved completely upon tissue healing with no implant residues in the human body. However, implant dissolution cannot occur too fast, as it would result in a dramatic decrease in implant stiffness before the completion of the tissue-healing process and can cause poisoning by corrosion products. Mg alloys are actively studied as a potential material for biodegradable implants. However, their exceptionally high corrosion rate in aqueous media and local alkalization of the surface during the degradation are the main limitation of their wide usage [1].

The application of biodegradable natural polymer coatings is a promising strategy for controlling and adjustment of the degradation profile of Mg alloys. It can also improve biocompatibility. Chitosan is a natural polymer that is increasingly used in biomedical applications due to its nontoxicity, excellent biocompatibility, biodegradability, and antibacterial activity. The significant advantage of chitosan is the possibility of its deposition by electrochemical techniques. It is essential for Mg implants because the coating can be obtained at low temperatures in a simple, cost-effective process.

This contribution focuses on the development of chitosan and chitosan-based composite coatings with phosphate ions via electrophoretic deposition on the WE43 and AZ31 magnesium alloys.

Chitosan of low, medium, and high molecular weights was examined. Chitosan solutions were prepared by dissolving chitosan powder (2 wt.%) in acetic acid (1 wt.%). Chitosan coatings were obtained by electrophoretic deposition under potential control from the solutions containing varying (10–90 vol.%) amounts of ethanol (99.9%). Chitosan-based composite coatings with phosphate ions were obtained from the solutions containing Na₃PO₄ or Na₂HPO₄ salts.

Formed coatings were characterized by scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. Corrosion properties of the obtained coatings in Hank's solution were evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, potentiodynamic polarization, and hydrogen release measurements. The best corrosion performance was achieved for chitosan coatings deposited from the solutions containing more than 50 vol.% of ethanol. The addition of phosphate ions significantly improved the corrosion performance of the coatings and allowed for tailoring the degradation profile depending on the concentration of phosphate and deposition time.

Based on these results, further steps for obtaining chitosan-based coatings with improved functionality and biodegradation profile, are formulated.

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References

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